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A Systemic Circular Model and Analysis applied to Innovative Sustainable Recycling of Thermoplastics

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Introduction: The recycling sector and its related market are one of most turbulent and nowadays the most strategic areas for the recovery of thermoplastics after its first use, so important for the environment and resources conservation. One of the main problems faced globally by the industry is the higher cost of recycled plastic materials compared to virgin plastic from fossil fuel combined with a very low recycling rate. Part of this question is due to the shortage of proper infrastructure for collecting and sorting the used plastics, not to mention technical and environmental issues regarding mechanical and chemical recycling of thermoplastics. The situation is compounded by a widespread linear, cost and profit-oriented mentality without any social and environmental consideration that guides primarily the recyclers and brand owners and a huge general paradoxical mismatching between where and how plastic is discarded, mainly in the western world, and where and how plastic is recycled, mainly in Asia (1).

Methods: In order to close these gaps and address these many systemic issues in the plastic value chain, the adoption of a holistic, complex system approach that better understands the different values, norms and behaviours among the key stakeholders is paramount. This allows, in connection also to a set of basic dynamic holistic indicators introduced, a systemic change in a more evident and emerging awareness of the interdependence of actions and decisions and their impacts. In taking a complex system perspective in modelling these issues, there is the realization of the nature of socio-economic interconnections as a non-linear synergetic process in a dynamic non-equilibrium of chaos within order, order within chaos similar to biological systems. And like them, they lead to unpredictable consequences that in turn feedback to influence individual actions in an endless cycle of adaptation and evolution (2).

Results & Discussions: New innovations for the recycling industry are required. Such innovations should identify ways to design and develop processes and products that go beyond traditional recycling technologies and systems to find new cost-competitive uses for plastic waste streams that are currently too expensive to process. The example, analysis and evaluation are presented of a novel company which has discovered a way to regenerate unsorted residual municipal general waste into new highly recyclable thermoplastics material for different industrial uses distinct from traditional types of plastics. Such a solution not only addresses the issues of collection and sorting, but also provides more localized solutions for waste (3).

Conclusions: The work outlines a systemic circular model for the plastic value chain to support innovations and a greater awareness of the context and interdependence of actions and decisions among the different key actors. In this way gaps are identified and delivered within the current system and circular solutions that disrupt the status quo are enabled.

Keywords: *Circular economy, Systemic thinking and complexity, Innovation, Plastic and recycling industry, Cultural change*

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